

DFG to OECD subject classification Mapping

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Authors:

- Kristian Garza; Datacite; kgarza@datacite.org;
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3484-6875>
- Dorothea Strecker; Berlin School of Library and Information Science,
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin; dorothea.strecker@hu-berlin.de;
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9754-3807>
- Anton Ninkov, École des sciences de l'information | School of Information
Studies, Université d'Ottawa | University of Ottawa, aninkov@uottawa.ca,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8276-7656>
- Kathleen Gregory, University of Vienna, University of Ottawa,
kathleen.gregory@univie.ac.at, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5475-8632>
- Rouven Schabinger, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, schabinger@kit.edu,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0249-7917>

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Introduction

Many DOI metadata deposits do not include standardized subject classification metadata¹. In response to the lack of standardization, DataCite has begun mapping different subject classification vocabularies to a common vocabulary: the OECD Revised Field of Science and Technology (OECD FOS) classification in the Frascati Manual. One of the many vocabularies yet to be mapped is the subject classification of the German Research Foundation, the DFG. The Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data) uses the DFG subject classification to classify data repositories. Members from DataCite, re3data, and the Make Data Count project, formed a task force to address this problem. The Taskforce has developed a candidate correspondence mapping between the DFG subject classification and the OECD FOS classification. This report presents how the task force generated the DFGtoOECD mapping, the final result, and the identified alignment issues.

The mapping will enable systems integrations, individuals, or organizations to map resources classified using notations of the DFG subject classification to notations of the OECD FOS. This mapping will form the basis of other mappings DataCite uses to standardize subject information in DOI metadata deposits. A potential implication of this effort could be that more initiatives will start working towards open classification systems for the scholarly communication space.

Background

This mapping is the link between two classification systems covering research disciplines: the DFG subject classification and the OECD FOS.

The DFG uses the DFG subject classification to organize funding programs and grant applications². The DFG subject classification has four levels: scientific area (4), subject area (14), and review board (48); the entire subject classification comprises 213 subjects at the lowest hierarchical level. This subject classification system is

¹ Garza, K. (2021). Datacite/frascati-mappings: Mappings of subject area classifications to the OECD fields of Science. GitHub. Retrieved February 15, 2022, from <https://github.com/datacite/frascati-mappings>

² The DFG Fachsystematik . DFG, German Research Foundation -. (2014, August). Retrieved February 9, 2022, from https://web.archive.org/web/20140901204254/http://dfg.de/en/dfg_profile/statutory_bodies/review_boards/subject_areas/index.jsp

continuously adjusted every four years in connection with the elections of the DFG Review Boards. The subject classification is also used by re3data (re3data.org) to classify repositories by discipline. Most repositories in re3data are assigned at least one notation at the third level of the classification.

The revised Field of Science and Technology classification is part of the Frascati Manual³. The manual recommends that the major fields of science and technology should be adopted as the functional fields of a scientific classification system. This classification should be used for R&D expenditures of the government, higher education, and PNP (Private NonProfit) sectors and, if possible, of the BE (Business enterprise) sector and for personnel data in all industries. However, the current implementation can be characterized as quite diverse across countries. The FOS classification includes six top-level categories and 42 subcategories. As of 2020, Datacite recommends classifying academic resources by subject using the FOS classification.

Methodology

The specifications of the DFG subject classification and OECD FOS on which the mapping DFGtoOECD is based are:

- DFG Fachsystematik (August 2014)
- OECD (Feb 2007)[DSTI/EAS/STP/NESTI(2006)19/FINAL]

DFGtoOECD builds upon these specifications to provide the most comprehensive and accurate mapping of notations as possible.

The process by which the DFGtoOECD was created followed five steps. We created a candidate correspondence mapping using the specification and documentation above mentioned—a separate group reviewed the candidate correspondence in three rounds. Several alignment issues were brought up and documented (see next section). Finally, we opened the final version of the candidate correspondence to

³ OECD.Revised Field of Science and Technology (Fos) Classification in the Frascati Manual. (2007) Directorate for Science, Technology, and Industry Committee for Scientific and Technological Policy. Retrieved February 7, 2022, from <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf>

public comments on the PID Forum website (pidforum.org⁴) and multiple social networks from 2021-09-01 to 2021-10-01. The community provided no comments during that period.

As a general rule, only the higher levels of granularity in both vocabularies were mapped. One exception was made for one of the notations, and that will be discussed in the next section.

Summary of alignment issues

During the review round, a few alignment issues were discovered. The issues were considered non-critical, but users of the mapping should take note of them when implementing the mapping. The issues stem from the fact that (1) the interdisciplinary subjects are modeled differently in the both classifications, (2) the classifications are structured differently, and (3) the classifications were developed for different reasons (OECD was developed for measuring R&D and DFG for managing grants). Some examples for issues include:

- Hierarchies are modeled differently in the two classifications. For example, Social Sciences was the only case where a notation of the lowest level of granularity in the OECD FOS was used in the mapping.
- The Astronomy notation in the DFG subject classification maps to the notation “physical sciences; other” in OECD FOS. As a result a large research discipline is subsumed in a residual category.
- OECD FOS differentiates between humans and animals in biomedical and biotechnological categories.

Mapping summary

The final mapping maps all notations of the DFG to at least one notation in OECD FOS. Biological Sciences and medicine are the OECD FOS notations with the most DFG notations mapped. Only eight DFG notations map to only one other OECD FOS notation. Fig. 1 shows the distribution of DFG notations mapped to OECD notations.

⁴ <https://pidforum.org/t/dfg-oecd-vocabulary-mapping-open-for-comments/1842>

Fig 1. Distribution of DFG notations mapped to OECD notations.

The mapping can be found on Github <https://github.com/datacite/frascati-mappings>⁵. Additionally, the task force developed an adapted mapping between the current version of the DFG subject classification (released in 2021⁶) and OECD FOS, which is available in the vocabulary editing tool cocoda.⁷

⁵ Garza, K. (2021). Datacite/frascati-mappings: Mappings of subject area classifications to the OECD fields of Science. GitHub. Retrieved February 15, 2022, from <https://github.com/datacite/frascati-mappings>

⁶https://web.archive.org/web/20220121054141/https://www.dfg.de/en/dfg_profile/statutory_bodies/review_boards/subject_areas/index.jsp

⁷ Verbundzentrale des GBV. (2015). Cocoda. Go to start page. Retrieved February 15, 2022, from <https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/>